

Entropy dynamics in thresholded neural state space

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Abstract

Entropy can be used to characterize probability distributions evolving across neural state space. However, when entropy is measured inside a threshold-defined region, the selected region itself may change over time. Using Reynolds transport theorem, we show that the entropy-rate associated with a density-thresholded sub-region of state space separates into two contributions: an interior entropy-density change term and a moving-boundary term caused by expansion or contraction of the thresholded region. We first validate this decomposition in a stochastic double-well system, where the measured entropy-rate inside the thresholded region is accurately reconstructed from the sum of the interior and boundary-motion terms. We then apply the same framework to two-photon imaging data from murine visual cortex and show that the boundary-motion term accounts for $\sim 90\%$ of the interior entropy-density change term. These results indicate that the motion of a threshold boundary through neural state space results in a separable geometric contribution to measured entropy dynamics.

Introduction

The time-dependent state of a neural system can be represented as a point in a high-dimensional state space, with coordinates corresponding to activity variables such as firing rates, fluorescence signals, or neuroimaging-derived metrics. As the system evolves, it traces trajectories through state space, building up time-dependent probability densities^{1,2}.

Entropy is a natural tool for characterizing such distributions, quantifying how broadly neural activity is spread across possible states³. Entropy-based measures have been widely applied in systems neuroscience to characterize spontaneous cortical activity, altered states of consciousness and cognitive variability⁴⁻⁷. Probability currents and associated entropy production have also been used to describe processes associated with neural dynamics⁸. These studies treat neural activity as an evolving probability distribution with temporal structure encoding information about underlying circuit organization.

A common step in neuroimaging analyses is to restrict attention to a subset of state space by thresholding the estimated probability density — retaining only states with probabilities exceeding a chosen threshold⁹. For example, thresholding is routinely used in cluster-based inference, where results are known to be sensitive to the threshold choice. In state space analyses of population activity, density thresholding similarly defines which states are considered dynamically

relevant at a given time. In such analyses, it is implicitly assumed that statistical quantities like entropy, computed over the threshold-defined subset, provide insight into the system's intrinsic dynamics. However, this assumption overlooks a critical detail: as the density evolves, the boundary of the thresholded region expands and contracts — thus including or excluding states over time. As such, changes in entropy reflect not only neural dynamics internal to the region but also changes due to the shifting geometry of the threshold boundary itself.

Using Reynolds transport theorem, we separate dynamic entropy into two contributions arising due to: 1) changes in density within the thresholded region, and 2) changes in density due to the motion of the thresholded region through state space^{10,11}. We validate this two-term decomposition in a simulated stochastic system and then apply it to empirical two-photon imaging data from mouse visual cortex.

Methods

Thresholding state space: The state of a neural system is represented by a vector $x(t)$ with components corresponding to activity variables such as voltage or image intensity. The associated state space X consists of all possible states, such that $x(t) \in X$. If we track the system's evolution over sufficient time, we can define an entropy density $\sigma(x, t)$ in terms of a probability density $\rho(x, t)$ over state space:

$$\sigma = -\rho \log \rho \quad (1)$$

where we take ρ to be dimensionless after normalization by a reference density.

This entropy density obeys a local balance equation:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} = \Pi - \nabla \cdot J \quad (2)$$

where $\Pi(x, t)$ is a local entropy source or production density and $J(x, t)$ is an entropy current^{12,13}.

Eq. (2) states that if entropy density increases, this could either be due to an influx of entropy current, or due to entropy changing locally at a rate Π . Note that when $\Pi = 0$, Eq. (2) reduces to a conservation law $\partial \sigma / \partial t + \nabla \cdot J = 0$, in which case entropy can only increase in a local region if it flows in from elsewhere in state space.

In the empirical decomposition below, Π and J are not estimated separately — doing so would require knowledge of the Fokker-Planck operator governing the density evolution. Instead, the two-term decomposition in Eq. (19) is implemented directly from the estimated density field, without requiring access to the underlying drift or diffusion.

We then define a sub-region of state space $R(t) \subset X$ created by thresholding. Specifically, only points in state space for which the probability density exceeds a constant threshold value c are retained:

$$R(t) = \{x \in X: \rho(x, t) > c\} \quad (3)$$

Note that, unlike the threshold value c itself, $R(t)$ is not necessarily constant. This is because points in state space that are above threshold can fall below and points that are below threshold

can rise above. In other words, the threshold contour $\partial R(t)$ itself can change in time, where the density takes the fixed value c on the boundary of the sub-region:

$$\partial R(t) = \{x \in X: \rho(x, t) = c\} \quad (4)$$

The thresholded region $R(t)$ has a volume given by:

$$V(t) = \int_{R(t)} dv \quad (5)$$

where dv is a state space volume element.

Similarly, its boundary has a surface area

$$A(t) = \int_{\partial R(t)} da \quad (6)$$

where da is a state space surface area element.

Eqs. (1) and (4) give the entropy density at the boundary of the thresholded sub-region:

$$\sigma_{\partial R} = -c \log c \quad (7)$$

and the total entropy contained within the sub-region is:

$$S = \int_{R(t)} \sigma dv \quad (8)$$

Thresholded entropy evolution: To track how this entropy evolves, we differentiate Eq. (8) in time

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{R(t)} \sigma dv \quad (9)$$

We then use Reynolds transport theorem to separate the entropy rate into two contributions due to: 1) changes of entropy density internal to the moving sub-region (S_I), and 2) motion of the sub-region boundary (S_B):

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{dS_I}{dt} + \frac{dS_B}{dt} \quad (10)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (10) describes the contribution from local change of entropy density within the thresholded state space region:

$$\frac{dS_I}{dt} = \int_{R(t)} \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} dv \quad (11)$$

Using Eqs. (2) and (11), we obtain:

$$\frac{dS_I}{dt} = \int_{R(t)} \Pi dv - \int_{R(t)} \nabla \cdot J dv \quad (12)$$

where we can convert the second term on the right-hand side to a surface integral using the divergence theorem to give:

$$\frac{dS_I}{dt} = \int_{R(t)} \Pi dv - \int_{\partial R(t)} J \cdot n da \quad (13)$$

where n is an outward-pointing unit normal vector.

Next, we address the second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (10), which is given by:

$$\frac{dS_B}{dt} = \int_{\partial R(t)} \sigma u \cdot n da \quad (14)$$

where $u(x, t)$ is the velocity of the moving boundary of the thresholded sub-region of state space.

We know from Eq. (7) that the entropy density is constant along the threshold boundary, meaning we can re-write Eq. (14) as

$$\frac{dS_B}{dt} = \sigma_{\partial R} \int_{\partial R(t)} u \cdot n da \quad (15)$$

where the integral on the right-hand side of Eq. (15) can be written in terms of the volume of the thresholded region V defined in Eq. (5):

$$\frac{dS_B}{dt} = \sigma_{\partial R} \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (16)$$

Substituting Eqs. (13) and (16) into Eq. (10) gives the entropy balance for the density-thresholded region:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \int_{R(t)} \Pi dv - \int_{\partial R(t)} J \cdot n da + \sigma_{\partial R} \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (17)$$

We now use the volume V and surface area A from Eqs. (5) and (6) to define the following geometry-normalized quantities:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{s}_{total} &= \frac{1}{V} \frac{dS}{dt} \\ \bar{\pi} &= \frac{1}{V} \int_{R(t)} \Pi dv \\ \bar{j} &= \frac{1}{A} \int_{\partial R(t)} J \cdot n da \\ \bar{s}_{thresh} &= \sigma_{\partial R} \frac{d}{dt} \log V \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

This normalization is useful when comparing thresholded regions of different sizes, since larger regions may show larger entropy changes simply because they occupy more state space volume.

Re-writing Eq. (17) in terms of the quantities in Eq. (18) gives:

$$\bar{s}_{total} = \bar{\pi} - \gamma \bar{j} + \bar{s}_{thresh} \quad (19)$$

where $\gamma = A/V$ is the surface-to-volume ratio (SVR), quantifying the thresholded boundary exposure.

The SVR γ provides a geometric intuition for when boundary motion matters most. Regions with high values of γ — such as thin, elongated sub-regions of state space — will exhibit larger boundary-motion contributions relative to their internal dynamics, even when the underlying density evolution is similar.

The expression in Eq. (19) separates the total entropy change per unit state space volume (\bar{s}_{total}) into the three contributions:

1. the internal entropy source/production density $\bar{\pi}$
2. the SVR γ -weighted boundary entropy current \bar{j}
3. the contribution from the expansion/contraction of the thresholded region \bar{s}_{thresh}

The third term is a direct consequence of the thresholding operation, which results in the sub-regions time-dependence. Were we instead to use a fixed sub-region — e.g., by pre-defining a volume in state space — we could simply bring the derivative in Eq. (9) inside the integral, rather than having to apply Reynolds transport theorem.

Synthetic data: We next tested whether the proposed moving boundary entropy correction can be recovered from synthetic state space data. To this end, we used a density-estimation and subsequent thresholding procedure for a two-dimensional stochastic system, following the form of Langevin stochastic dynamics^{14,15}:

$$\begin{aligned} dx_1 &= (x_1 - x_1^3)dt + \sqrt{2D}dW_1 \\ dx_2 &= -\lambda x_2 dt + \sqrt{2D}dW_2 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Here, D is a diffusion coefficient, dW is a two-dimensional Wiener process, and λ controls the strength of confinement in the x_2 direction. This system provides a minimal model of state space dynamics, while also allowing for noise and metastability.

10^5 trajectories were initialized near the left well of Eq. (20) and an associated entropy density calculated. The time-dependent sub-region in state space was then tracked for a series of fixed density thresholds. Values of moving boundary entropy predicted by our model were compared with values estimated from synthetic data across thresholds.

Empirical data: We next applied the thresholded entropy framework to resting-state two-photon imaging data collected within the visual cortex across five mice¹⁶. Each recording consists of a fluorescence movie together with an anatomical map assigning pixels to visual cortical areas. Each retained fluorescence trace was z-scored over time to have zero mean and unit variance. Linear detrending was used to reduce slow imaging drift, and the analysis was repeated without

detrending as a sensitivity check. We also used three sliding-window lengths, corresponding to 10, 20, and 30 s, to assess robustness with respect to temporal scale.

At each time point, the visual cortex was represented by an activity vector with one component per retained pixel. Principal component (PC) analysis was then applied, yielding a two-dimensional neural state space, within which all subsequent analyses were performed. A time-dependent probability density was estimated in this 2D state space using sliding temporal windows. Within each window, the distribution of state space trajectories was estimated on a fixed grid, smoothed with a Gaussian kernel, and normalized so that the density integrated to unity.

The grid was defined from the 1st to 99th percentile range of the full PC trajectory, with 25% padding, and the same grid was used across all windows for each mouse. This ensured that estimated volumes and entropy values were comparable over time. A sub-region of state space was defined by applying a fixed threshold to the estimated probability density. Thresholds were set at 5%, 10%, 20%, and 35% of the mean peak density. For each threshold and time window, we computed the state space volume and associated entropy.

We then decomposed the measured entropy-rate density into two terms. The first term captured the rate of change of entropy density at fixed state space positions within the thresholded region. The second term measured the contribution from the shifting boundary of the thresholded region itself. Root mean squared (RMS) magnitude ratios between the entropy density rates associated with the two terms were calculated. This allowed us to quantify the extent to which the moving-boundary term contributed to total entropy rate density.

Results

All results can be replicated using the publicly available data and accompanying code (see data and code availability).

Synthetic data: We first showed that the contour created by thresholding changes over time as the estimated density evolves (Fig. 1A). This confirms that a fixed density threshold defines a time-dependent state space region. We then tested whether the measured entropy-rate density inside this moving region could be predicted by our model in Eq. (19) (Fig. 1B). This predicted density consists of two independently computed terms: an interior entropy-density change term and a threshold-boundary term (Fig. 1C).

Fig. 1: A) Threshold contours in two-dimensional state space (x_1, x_2) at three time points (T_0, T_1, T_2) , illustrating that a fixed density threshold defines a time-dependent boundary as the estimated density evolves. **B)** Measured total entropy-rate density and its reconstruction from the sum of the internal and threshold-boundary terms. **C)** The separate internal and threshold-boundary contributions to entropy-rate density.

Across all thresholds, the maximum unnormalized relative error between measured and predicted total density was 0.55% and the maximum volume-normalized relative error was 0.77%. The threshold-boundary term reached up to 21.8% of the RMS magnitude of the interior term. These results show that the entropy of a thresholded state space region contains a separate quantifiable contribution from the expansion or contraction of the region itself.

Empirical data: The first two principal components (PCs) captured between 43.8% and 63.8% of the full population activity variance in the two-photon imaging data across the five mice. Time-dependent probability densities were estimated in this two-dimensional PC state space and density-thresholded sub-regions were defined across sliding temporal windows.

Applying a fixed density threshold in state space produced a time-dependent boundary (Fig. 2A). The measured total entropy rate was reconstructed by the sum of contributions: 1) internal to the thresholded region and 2) due to the moving threshold boundary (Fig. 2B). The two terms showed comparable magnitudes over time (Fig. 2C).

We show a segment of the evolving probability density and associated motion of the threshold-defined boundary through neural state space, together with the corresponding two-photon murine fluorescence activity in Supplementary Movie 1. The threshold-boundary contribution was substantial across all tested thresholds. The thresholded-to-internal RMS ratios were 0.92 ± 0.05 , 0.95 ± 0.05 , 0.94 ± 0.07 , and 0.92 ± 0.13 for the 5%, 10%, 20%, and 35% density thresholds, respectively.

Fig. 2: A) Threshold contours in two-dimensional PC state space (PC1, PC2) at three sliding-window centers (T_0, T_1, T_2) for one mouse, showing that the threshold boundary shifts position as the estimated density evolves. **B)** Measured total entropy-rate density and its reconstruction from the sum of the internal and threshold-boundary terms. **C)** Separate internal and threshold-boundary contributions to total entropy-rate density.

Discussion

Thresholding is a widely used technique in neuroscience for restricting analyses to sub-region of state space with probability densities exceeding a chosen value. In this work, we demonstrate that entropy is affected not only by changes internal to such a sub-region, but also by motion of the threshold boundary as it sweeps across state space. This motion-dependence means that entropy calculations over thresholded probability distributions do not reflect a fixed set of states. Instead, as a sub-region expands or contracts, new states are continuously included or excluded, resulting in a quantifiable geometric contribution to entropy dynamics.

The sensitivity of statistical analyses to threshold choice is a well-known methodological issue in neuroimaging, where varying a threshold can change which clusters or regions of interest in the

brain are identified^{9,17}. Our focus differs: rather than examining how results vary across different threshold values, we ask what is being measured after a single threshold has been chosen and held fixed. Although the threshold value remains constant, the associated suprathreshold region changes shape and size in state space as the underlying probability density evolves. This means that entropy associated with this probability density includes a contribution from motion of the integration domain itself — i.e., the geometry of the sub-region in state space.

Neural dynamics are often described as evolving activity patterns in low-dimensional state space^{1,2,18}. For instance, probability currents and associated entropy production have been used to characterize non-equilibrium processing in the brain^{8,19,20}. Our results complement this literature by quantifying a boundary-motion contribution to entropy that arises specifically by virtue of a thresholding operation. Failing to account for this boundary-motion term risks conflating two distinct contributions: 1) changes in entropy density internal to the selected region and 2) changes in the geometry of the region itself. In the mouse visual cortex data, the internal term was of similar magnitude to the geometric term. This indicates that a substantial component of measured entropy-rate dynamics arises from changes in the geometry of the thresholded state space region itself, rather than solely from changes in the underlying neural activity.

Supp. Movie 1:

A) *Widefield fluorescence activity from mouse visual cortex with retinotopically defined cortical areas: primary visual cortex (V1), posteromedial (PM), anteromedial (AM), rostromedial (RL), anterolateral (AL), and lateromedial (LM).*

B) *Time-dependent probability density estimated in two-dimensional principal-component (PC1 & PC2) state space derived from population fluorescence activity. The black contour denotes a fixed density (10% of the mean peak density), defining the thresholded state space region at each time point.*

C) *Decomposition of the total entropy-rate density into two terms accounting for internal and threshold-boundary contributions.*

Data availability

The two-photon murine visual cortex data is made available at the following repository:
https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Data_from_Functional_Parcillation_of_Mouse_Visual_Cortex_Using_Statistical_Techniques_Reveals_Response-Dependent_Clustering_of_Cortical_Processing_Areas_/13476522/1

Code availability

All code used in this study is made available at the following repository:
<https://github.com/allavailablepubliccode/threshold>

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